

ON THE INVESTIGATION FOR QUANTITY PRODUCTION OF IRON WHISKER

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The iron whisker is a single crystal with high purity and has high tensile strength. The whisker is potentially useful as fibers for composite materials and new electric materials in the future. The whisker has excellent properties, but the utilization is limited by un-uniformity of the length and the diameter.

The strength of experimental composite materials²⁾³⁾⁴⁾⁵⁾ with fibers or by uni-directional solidification with long fibers of carbon or boron are better than whiskers though the tensile strength of iron whisker is over twice that of long fiber carbon or boron.

This author investigated the mechanical properties uniformity of length, and thickness of quantity production whiskers by reduction of $\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ with hydrogen.¹⁾

Specifically, this report is on the application of gaseous curtain for the continuous production processing of iron whiskers and the growth mechanism.

On the application of gaseous curtain for the production process of iron whisker

A purpose of the apparatus is for the trial production of iron whisker. The apparatus has two gaseous curtains or inlet and outlet of batch furnace of Brenner type.⁶⁾

The apparatus for semicontinuous production of iron whisker

with gas curtain is shown in Fig. 1. Many gas curtain methods use the gas flame, air etc.⁷⁾

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of semicontinuous production apparatus for Iron whiskers.

The property of free jet flow are shown in Fig. 2, change of the jet flow, distance Z versus the center flow rate U_c of jet be able to express with the value of dimension less by the jet flow rate U_0 or $1/2$ of jet slot width A_0

$$U_c/U_0 = \sqrt{\phi(1/0.8 \cdot Z)} \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

where $\phi = Z/\sqrt{\pi} \int_0^t e^{-t^2} \cdot dt \dots\dots$ error function

$$Z = z/\frac{1}{2} A_0$$

Fig. 2. The property of free jetflow.

U_c, U_0 : m/sec A_0, z : m or mm

The distribution of jet flow by gas curtains is shown in Fig.3.

Fig. 3. Relation between center velocity at the free jet flow and Z(distance from jet slot).

The value of dimension less can be calculated with equation (1), that is center flow rate of jet is not changed at the distance of about 4.5 ~ 5 times from the jet ($Z = z/2 \cdot A_0 = 9 \sim 10$)

Therefore its using the approximate equation ($Z = z/2 \cdot A_0 > 28$)

$$U_c / U_0 = 3.74 / \sqrt{z} \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

These equations are shown in a dotted line in Fig.3.

The terminal velocity of jet flow of gases curtain can be calculated by the approximate equation. Generally the value of terminal velocity is better at upper 2.5 ~ 3 m/sec.

The velocity distribution of each slot of gas curtains are shown in Fig.4, and its almost equal value.

The results of investigation on the gases distribution in the furnace using gas curtains are shown in Fig.5 and Fig.6.

The mixed ratio of air is decreased with increase of flow rate of nitrogen gases from jet slot and the concentration of hydrogen gases in the furnace has not been effect at increase of flow rate, its almost constant on about 40% to total volume, moreover the gases in the furnace showed the concentration distribution with the density of each gas.

In the case of whisker production the low flow rate ($Re = 5$), requires the double or triple (threefold) gases curtain.

Fig. 4. Velocity distribution of each slot of gases curtain.

Fig. 5. Relation between jet flow velocity and gases concentration in furnace.

Fig. 6. Gases concentration of each part in furnace.

The authors have developed a continuous production process of iron whisker by gas curtains combined with multiple hinged doors. The gas seals are shown in Fig.7, and the investigated results of gas distributions in the furnace are shown in Fig.8 and Fig.9.

The results of trials on iron whisker growth by this furnace produced the basic data required for the quantity production.

Fig. 7. Schematic diagram of gases curtain combined with multiple hinged door.

Fig. 8. Relation between gases velocity at multiple hinged door and H₂ gases concentration in furnace.

On the continuous production of iron whiskers

A schematic sketch of the continuous production apparatus for iron whiskers is shown in Fig.10. The main components of this continuous production apparatus are as follows: the furnace has the gas seal system on the inlet and outlet of a batch furnace. This reaction furnace is separated into four zones, a heating zone which melts FeCl₂ and supplies molten FeCl₂ to a boat, a reducing zone which grows iron whisker, a cooling zone of whisker, and an automatic feeder.

The boat starts from the left hand side of the apparatus, which opens and closes the hinged door by itself and moves to the heating zone to supply molten FeCl₂ and grows iron whiskers while passing through the reduction zone. Then the boat is moved to the cooling zone and automatic feeder, which prevents contamination of the whisker from HCl vapor, which affects the stabilization of the whisker.

The effects of sealing by gas curtains are shown in Fig.11.

a) Relation between seal effect by gases curtain and gases concentration at center part in furnace

b) Relation between seal effect by gases curtain and gases concentration at lower part in furnace

Fig. 9. Relation between seal effect by gases curtain and gases concentration in furnace.

Fig. 10 Schematic diagram of continuous production apparatus for Iron whiskers.

Fig. 11. Relation between seal effect of gases curtain and H₂ flow rate.

The growth mechanism for iron whiskers and control of the growth

A growth mechanism for iron whiskers is thought to be as follows: a) the conception period for nucleus formation b) the period of length growth c) the period of thickness growth.

Generally a nucleus formation is by internal stress in material, and the dislocation or the twin on the surface of material, and by the irregular grain boundary.

The iron whisker growth is thought to be from the crystal in perfect ions during oxidation of material.

The chemical reaction of iron whisker growth is as follows at (PH₂O/PH₂>0.02):

This FeO is the formation on the wall of the boat, and the next reaction is as follows:

Reduced iron $Fe_{(s)}$ is adsorbed on the step with crystal imperfections of material, and iron whiskers grow up with repeat of this phenomenon.

This phenomenon of crystal growth can be illustrated as follows: a) a growth by screw dislocation b) a growth by catalytic action of the impurity.

The growth velocity of iron whisker at $700^{\circ}C$ was over $25\mu/sec$ by microscopic observation.

The production of fine whiskers requires the control of reaction time, the volume of supplies of molten $FeCl_2$ and minute control of partial pressure PH_2/PH_2O .

On the growth of iron whisker and crystal orientation

There are intimate relations between the crystal orientation and its cross section form of iron whiskers. The investigation results with Laue X-ray method are shown in Table 1. Many iron whiskers indicated crystal orientation $\langle 100 \rangle$.

Table 1. Results of investigation by Laue method

Samples No.	crystal orientation	crystal plane	sectional form	measure (μ)	a/b
1	$\langle 100 \rangle$	(100)	rectangle	70X65	1.08
2	$\langle 100 \rangle$	(100)	:	80X77	1.04
3	$\langle 100 \rangle$	(100)	:	40X50	1.25
4	$\langle 100 \rangle$	(100)	:	68X72	1.06
5	$\langle 100 \rangle$	(100)	:	84X150	1.79
6	$\langle 100 \rangle$	(100)	:	64X153	2.4
7	$\langle 100 \rangle$	(100)	quad rate	70X70	1
8	$\langle 100 \rangle$	(100)	:	30X30	1
9	$\langle 100 \rangle$	(100)	:	30X30	1

The relation between the crystal orientation and a/b (ratio of the two sides of quadrilateral) are shown in Fig.12.

In the case of $a/b > 3$ is a rectangle, and its crystal orientation $\langle 100 \rangle$ and has a crystal plane (100).

Fig. 12. Relation between the crystal orientation and ratio of quad-rhedral (a/b).

Conclusion

1) The continuous production furnace is able to produce whiskers in a reducing atmosphere similar to the batch furnace of Brenner type.

2) The thickness of whiskers can be regulated by control of the gas flow rates.

3) The growth of whiskers is controlled by the vapor pressure of FeCl_2 , and the vapor pressure of about 10 mm Hg produces the best results.

4) The growth mechanism of whiskers is a vapor growth which passes through the process of nucleus formation, length growth and thickness growth.

5) These iron whiskers may be divided according to their growth mechanism into two specific types; that is, whisker with high purity, high tensile strength of 400 to 600 Kg/mm^2 and low tensile strength.

The former can be produced at the rate of 0.4 to 0.6 Kg per day and the latter 2 to 3 Kg per day when using an experimental apparatus for quantity production.

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